

OCEAN ICE News – March 2026

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to March's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as an OCEAN ICE publication, OCEAN ICE at Ocean Science Meeting 2026, and highlighting February's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in March and April. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in April!

Meet the Team: Rūta Hamilton

Check out our latest 'Meet the Team' feature on Rūta Hamilton, the Post-Award Programme Manager at UK Research and Innovation – British Antarctic Survey.

Read the feature on Rūta [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE at Ocean Science Meeting 2026, Glasgow

During the Ocean Science Meeting 2026, there was project members from OCEAN ICE who presented their current work and research.

Zhetao Tan (post-doc in WP5) showed the latest progress on the South Atlantic long-term changes in different water masses.

David Chandler presented results mainly focused on the climatic impacts of freshwater fluxes from Antarctica into the Southern Ocean. As well as Committed Southern Ocean warming and implications for the Antarctic Ice Sheet following emission cessation. This study quantified how much long-term (centennial-scale) Southern Ocean warming we expect after a zero-carbon transition.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Publication: Mapping tipping risks from Antarctic ice basins under global warming

The Antarctic ice sheet does not behave as one single tipping element, but as a set of interacting basins with different critical thresholds. This is the finding of a new study by the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK) and the Max Planck Institute of Geoanthropology (MPI-GEA). With today's warming, about 40 percent of the ice stored in West Antarctica may already be committed to long-term loss, while parts of East Antarctica could cross thresholds at moderate levels of warming between 2 to 3°C compared to pre-industrial levels, contributing significantly to global long-term sea-level rise.

Read the full article [here](#).

 OCEAN:ICE

OCEAN:ICE Paper Published:

**Mapping tipping risks from
Antarctic ice basins under global
warming**

 **Funded by
the European Union**

 **UK Research
and Innovation**

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – February

Climate Coffee with Linus Vogt on Increased future ocean heat uptake constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent

A talk with Linus about his recent publication: <https://esd.copernicus.org/articles/1...> The ocean takes up over 90% of the excess heat stored in the Earth system as a result of anthropogenic climate change, which has led to sea level rise and an intensification of marine extreme events. However, despite their importance for informing climate policy, future ocean heat uptake (OHU) projections still strongly differ between climate models. Here, we provide improved global OHU projections by identifying a relationship between present-day Antarctic sea ice extent (SIE) and future OHU across an ensemble of 28 state-of-the-art climate models. Models with more sea ice at present also simulate a colder Southern Hemisphere climate state in general, allowing a larger shift in atmospheric and ocean warming. This regional change affects global warming and heat uptake via a northward-propagating cloud feedback. Combining this relationship between historical Antarctic sea ice extent and future global OHU with satellite observations of Antarctic sea ice reduces the uncertainty of OHU projections under future emission scenarios by 12%–33%. Moreover, we show that an underestimation of present-day Antarctic sea ice in the latest generation of climate models results in an underestimation of future OHU by 3%–14%, an underestimation of global cloud feedback by 19%–32%, and an underestimation of global atmospheric warming by 6%–7%. This emergent constraint is based on a strong coupling between Antarctic sea ice, deep-ocean temperatures, and Southern Hemisphere sea surface temperatures and cloud cover in climate models. Our study reveals how the present-day Southern Ocean state impacts future climate change and suggests that previous constraints based on warming trends over recent decades have underestimated future warming and ocean heat uptake.

19 February 2026 | 15:00 - 15:45 CET

Online

Linus Vogt

(NYU, Sorbonne, LOCEAN)

**Increased future ocean heat uptake
constrained by Antarctic sea ice extent**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch, the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in November and December, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Giulia Bonino on Mediterranean summer marine heatwaves triggered by weaker winds under subtropical ridges

26 March 2026, 16:00 – 16:45 (CET)

The banner features a smiling woman on the left, a sunset over the ocean in the center, and a blue sky with clouds on the right. Text elements include: 'CLIMATE ACTION DAYS' in a red box, 'EUROPEAN CLIMATE PACT' in a blue box, '26 March 4 pm Climate Coffee' in a yellow box, and 'Mediterranean summer marine heatwaves triggered by weaker winds under subtropical ridges' in a dark blue box. Logos at the bottom include the Danish Meteorological Institute, ECRA, Obs Sea 4 clim, OCEAN:ICE, and the European Union. A red 'Join us!' button is on the right.

Climate Coffee with Jens Terhaar on Record sea surface temperature jump in 2023–2024 unlikely but not unexpected

23 April 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

23 April 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Jens Terhaar
(University Bern)

Record sea surface temperature jump
in 2023–2024 unlikely but not
unexpected

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 9th - 13th March 2026, [CMIP 2026 Meeting](#), Kyoto, Japan
- 22nd - 25th March 2026, [ISMIP7 Copenhagen workshop](#), Copenhagen, Denmark
- 3rd - 8th May 2026, [EGU 2026](#), Vienna, Austria
- 8th - 19th August 2026, [SCAR Open Science Conference & Meetings](#), Norway, Oslo
- 17th - 19th August 2026, [FRISP Meeting 2026](#), Sweden, Kristineberg

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

 OCEAN:ICE

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